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Presentation Format: *Flash Talk (5 minutes, maximum of 3 slides)*

Presentation Day: **Thursday**

Presentation Time: **2:45:00 PM**

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ABSTRACT:

In the tourism sector of Sri Lanka, terms such as geo conservation, geo-diversity, and geo-tourism are novel. Implementation of the required strategies to promote the geo endowment of Sri Lanka has the potential to enhance international recognition. This study was carried out along with a proposal for the implementation of the geo-tourism site focusing on the wind-powered iron smelting sites in Samanalawewa, Balangoda, Sri Lanka. The uniqueness, distinct culture, natural splendor, and the well-known hospitality of this area makes it an ideal tourist destination. Many tourists are attracted to the area mainly due to the ecotourism or the natural splendor of the entire Belihuloya region. The awareness among both local and foreign communities on the specific geological site is poor thus gaining less attention from the visitors to the area. Similarly, the information gathered during the field excursions shows that there is a high potential to initiate the industry and bring back the global recognition that existed earlier.

The remnants of the iron smelted sites are found even today. The sites have been even scientifically investigated with the intervention of foreign scientists for the uniqueness of the techniques used. The industry is believed to have prevailed with the interconnection of geomorphology, community and the technological aspects. It has proven the use of unique geomorphology of the area to acquire the perfect wind direction to power the furnaces. The significance of the industry was found to be remarkable since well-known Damascus steel has been exported from Sri Lanka. This steel is recognized as a special type due to the properties given to the tools or weapons made. Till today the story behind the wind-powered iron smelting in the Samanalawewa area and the evidence that persisted are bound to the community of the area and not revealed outside. Most of the areas are defunct today and the villagers have dropped their interest in the field.

Thus, the conveyance of the awareness to the people out and emphasizing the importance is identified as a key requirement with the prevailing invaluable geological assets. With a view to achieving this objective, an investigation was done and a management plan is proposed consisting of the collection of information from documented records, preparation of the maps, field visits to a selected site of interest, preparation of the management plan and the designing of sightseeing guide.